

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON GROUP COHESION AND QUALITY OF DECISION-MAKING IN THE SELECTED BARANGAYS USING IRVING JANIS' GROUPTHINK THEORY

VIDA CHARM G. LAMPADIO, RONA D. ALEJO, NARSAL M. FORONDA, JR.,
JESSA MARIE L. ALVAREZ

BA Political Science
Isabela State University-Cauayan Campus

ABSTRACT

This research study examined group cohesion and decision-making quality in three selected barangays in the Philippines specifically San Miguel, San Bonifacio, and Raniag in Burgos, Isabela. Irving Janis' Groupthink Theory served as the theoretical framework for the study, which adopted a qualitative approach with a descriptive phenomenological research design. In-depth interviews and observations were utilized as primary data-gathering methods. The study revealed a strong sense of group cohesion among the barangay officials in the selected areas. However, this high level of cohesion often led to the occurrence of groupthink during the decision-making process, with symptoms such as the illusion of unanimity and self-censorship observed among the officials. Various challenges and factors contributing to groupthink were identified, including conflicting personal preferences, power dynamics, communication barriers, and a lack of diverse perspectives. To address these issues, the study highlighted strategies implemented by the barangays to prevent groupthink and improve decision-making. These strategies included promoting open communication, valuing diverse opinions, comprehensive planning, fairness, and continuous education. The study recommended that barangay officials actively work towards preventing groupthink by encouraging critical evaluation, independent thinking, and constructive dialogue. By embracing strategies such as open communication, involving diverse perspectives, thorough planning, fairness, collaboration with external sources, and continuous education, decision-making practices can be enhanced, and the negative consequences of groupthink can be avoided. Ultimately, this study contributes to the existing knowledge by filling the research gap on group cohesion and groupthink in the specific context of barangays in the Philippines. The findings provide valuable insights for improving decision-making practices and driving positive change in the local governance setting.

Keywords: *Decision-making, Group Cohesion, Groupthink, Irving Janis, Strategies, Phenomenon*

INTRODUCTION

Decision-making is crucial in various aspects of life, involving groups like project teams, businessmen, sports teams, religious congregations, and policymakers. These groups work collectively despite individual differences to reach a consensus. Collaboration is often beneficial in addressing crises, as multiple individuals can outperform one person (Brennan and Enns, 2015). Group decision-making, based on collaborative cognition, relies on each member's input for optimal outcomes. According to Schulze and Newell (2016), careful deliberation and unbiased generation of options are essential for effective group decision-making. However, in certain situations, involving more people can become a constraint when minimal debate or others' opinions are unnecessary (Umana & Okafor, 2019). Wright and Meadows (2012) characterized this as bounded rationality, which occurs when decisions are based on available information, leading to reconsideration or involving others in the decision-making process.

Moreover, Dipillo (2019) provided a definition of group cohesion as a process that emphasizes the unity and collaborative efforts of teams in achieving shared goals while attending to individual members' needs. While group cohesion is crucial for successful teamwork, it can also introduce challenges and setbacks, especially in the presence of groupthink. Coined by Irving Janis, an American psychologist, groupthink refers to a cognitive phenomenon observed in highly cohesive in-groups, wherein the desire for consensus outweighs a realistic consideration of all possible alternatives.

Within the Philippine context, a barangay comprises various officials responsible for governmental projects, services, and community representation. Although extensive international research has explored group cohesion and groupthink, their examination within the Philippine context remains limited. Consequently, the concept of groupthink may be unfamiliar, thus, this study sought to contribute to existing knowledge by localizing these concepts and examining group cohesion and groupthink specifically within the barangay context.

Moreover, the study aimed to shed light on the potential problems associated with the groupthink phenomenon and its impact on decision-making quality within barangays. By exploring the perceptions of barangay officials regarding group cohesion and their experiences in making collective decisions, the study sought to identify the antecedents that contributed to the emergence of groupthink. The application of Irving Janis' Groupthink Theory allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the decision-making processes and their relationship to group cohesion.

Specifically, this study aimed to compare and analyze the group cohesion of the three selected barangays specifically San Miguel, San Bonifacio, and Raniag in Burgos, Isabela, and their decision-making quality through Irving Janis' Groupthink Theory. First, it seeks to know how barangay officials perceive the cohesion within their group, what are their experiences in making collective decisions, and what are the antecedents that caused the rise of groupthink in the barangays' collective decision-making process. Moreover, it also delved on the potential outcomes of group cohesion and groupthink's emergence on the barangay's decision-making quality, and to their actions in preventing groupthink and strategies in improving their quality of decision-making. Ultimately, it explored on how barangay officials differ in their experiences and strategies in dealing with groupthink.

METHODS

In this comparative study, the researchers employed a qualitative approach with a descriptive phenomenological research design to analyze and compare group cohesion and decision-making quality in three selected barangays in Burgos, Isabela. The study focused on utilizing Janis' groupthink theory to examine the group dynamics within the barangays. Purposive sampling was used to select fifteen respondents, five from each barangay, who had relevant experiences and knowledge. Data was collected through in-depth interviews and observations, using a semi-structured interview guide with open-ended and follow-up questions. The gathered data was then transcribed, organized, interpreted, and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify patterns of meaning related to group cohesion and decision-making quality in the barangay setting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perception of the Barangay Officials on their Group Cohesion

The data from three barangays showed important themes on officials' group cohesion. A strong sense of belongingness is evident. In an in-depth interview, one of the respondents enthusiastically stated, "... *pag may okasyon ganon talagang tinatawag naman ako.*" (... whenever there are special occasions, they make it a point to include me and extend their invitations.) (Respondent 1, personal communication, April 29, 2023). The data aligns with Crickard et al.'s (2022) notion that group cohesion is evident when individuals feel a strong sense of belonging, form close interpersonal connections, and actively participate in collective tasks and social activities. Moreover, fostering active participation and collaboration, officials across all barangays feel connected to their groups, experiencing positive interactions and support.

Another prominent theme, particularly in Barangay San Bonifacio, is the social bond among officials, emphasizing enduring friendships beyond official roles. This bond promotes cooperation and support, contributing to positive relationships. One of them expressed, "... *talaga nga adda nabuo mi nga natibay friendship.*" (We were able to build a solid friendship) (Respondent 3, personal communication, April 29, 2023). Additionally, another respondent emphasized, "... *saka adda met ah ti friendship nga nabuo talaga kinyami.*" (A friendship has been established between us). (Respondent 5, personal communication, April 29, 2023). These data indicate a strong and enduring social bond among officials, characterized by camaraderie, trust, and support. This bond extends beyond their official roles, fostering cooperation and collaboration. Birt (2023) supports this data, highlighting the natural development of friendship, respect, and support among group members, strengthening their professional and personal connections.

Additionally, officials in all barangays perceive their colleagues as ideal co-members based on duty fulfillment and positive characteristics. They find personal satisfaction in serving the community and emphasize the importance of close relationships. Specifically, Respondent 15 from Barangay Raniag asserted, "... *tugma sila sa aking palagay dahil nga ginagawa naman nila ng maayos ang trabaho na nakaassign sa kanila.*" (... they are fit, in my opinion, because they do the job assigned to them well.) (Respondent 15, personal communication). This

finding aligns with a study by the University of Minnesota Libraries Publishing (2015), which suggests that cohesion is linked to the level of contentment among group members regarding their own performance and that of their team members.

While common themes exist, Barangay San Bonifacio stands out with its unique emphasis on social bonds and positive interpersonal qualities. These elements significantly contribute to the cohesion and positive relationships among officials in the said barangay emphasizing the importance of nurturing and acknowledging these aspects for effective group dynamics.

On the other hand, although specific examples from San Miguel and Raniag may not have been mentioned in the given context, it can be inferred that a sense of belongingness, positive interactions, and support are also prevalent in these barangays. The data suggest that officials in all three barangays perceive their colleagues as ideal co-members based on duty fulfillment and positive characteristics. They find personal satisfaction in serving the community and emphasize the importance of close relationships.

Thus, while Barangay San Bonifacio exhibits a unique emphasis on social bonds and positive interpersonal qualities, it is important to recognize that all three barangays share commonalities in terms of group cohesion. The study's data imply that fostering a sense of belonging, positive interactions, and support among officials is crucial for effective group dynamics in all barangays, including San Miguel and Raniag.

Groupthink Experiences Among Barangay Officials

The experiences of Barangay San Bonifacio, San Miguel, and Raniag reveal common patterns of groupthink. Doubts and uncertainties hindered decision-making, especially in complex situations or when lacking expertise. One respondent mentioned holding additional sessions to address doubts. He shared, "*Oo meron kaya minsan nagkakaroon kami ulit ng sesyon.*" (Yes, that is why we sometimes have another session.) (Respondent 3, personal communication, April 29, 2023). The findings relate to Merkhofer's (2019) idea that groupthink discourages expressing doubts and disagreements. Doubt poses a significant challenge in group decision-making, especially in complex problems or when lacking expertise. It can impede the decision-making process through hesitation and uncertainty.

Moreover, self-censorship due to fear of disapproval was observed in San Bonifacio and Raniag, hindering free expression of opinions. One respondent mentioned refraining from voicing thoughts to avoid angering the barangay chairman and fellow officials. This fear stems from potential negative consequences and its impact on relationships within the group. According to Ethics Unwrapped (n.d.), groupthink can influence us to prioritize harmony and consensus above individual judgment, potentially leading to unethical conduct.

Furthermore, challenges of seniority in service limited diversity in San Bonifacio and San Miguel, while gender stereotyping marginalized female officials' voices. Respondent 9 from San Miguel mentioned being the youngest and accepting the decisions of their elders, "*Kinyak met, siyak gamin ti kaubigan isu tangtanggapek nukwa lattan jay desisyon ti laklakay ta isuda ti mas ahead kinyak.*" (In my case, I am the youngest, so I just accept the decision of the elders because they are ahead of me.) (Respondent 9, April 27, 2023). Moreover, Respondent 4 in San Bonifacio asserted that there are only two female officials compared to their male counterparts. This gender imbalance suggests a potential lack of diverse perspectives and experiences, as well as the possibility of unequal representation of interests and concerns. This aligns with Cherry's (2022) notion that senior members in a group can create a power dynamic that discourages dissenting opinions and critical discussion. This dynamic may contribute to groupthink, as individuals hesitate to express their thoughts due to perceived lack of knowledge or the belief that more qualified members have already addressed the issues.

Also, blind obedience to authority impeded independent thinking in San Bonifacio, and the illusion of unanimity occurred in both San Miguel and Raniag when individuals remained silent. Respondent 3 shared, "*Nu ana ti ibaga ni chairman nukwa kit wen lattan siges lattan...*" (If the chairman says something, I just say yes and agree.) (Respondent 3, personal communication, April 29, 2023). The influence of the leader, particularly the chairman, on the decision-making process and behavior of barangay officials is evident in Respondent 3's response. This reliance on the leader's authority can hinder independent thinking and diverse viewpoints, contributing to groupthink. As mentioned by Decision Lab (2023), when there is a strong and influential leader and group members simply agree with the leader without evaluating alternate possibilities, groupthink is more likely to occur.

On the other hand, the illusion of unanimity occurs when individuals perceive false agreement within the group. This illusion arises when people stay silent or withhold their opinions, creating the perception of consensus. In the given context, Respondent 7 from San Miguel, or the person expressing this barrier, remained silent during

the session and followed the majority decision, even if they had a different opinion. This could be due to a desire to avoid conflict or to expedite the session's completion. This corroborates with the statement of Guanlao (2021), in which he emphasized that group unanimity doesn't guarantee genuine support for an idea. The illusion of unanimity occurs when individuals conform or stay silent, creating the perception of agreement.

The experiences of three barangays revealed common patterns of groupthink, indicating the presence of similar challenges in their decision-making processes. Doubts and uncertainties hindered decision-making in all three barangays, particularly in complex situations or when lacking expertise. Self-censorship due to fear of disapproval was observed in both San Bonifacio and Raniag, limiting the open expression of opinions. Challenges associated with seniority in service were present in San Bonifacio and San Miguel, restricting diversity in decision-making. Furthermore, gender stereotyping marginalized the voices of female officials, specifically in San Bonifacio. Blind obedience to authority was identified as a barrier to independent thinking in San Bonifacio, while the illusion of unanimity occurred in both San Miguel and Raniag when individuals chose to remain silent.

Antecedents Of Groupthink Emergence

In terms of decision-making as a cohesive group, all barangays experience the risk of overconfidence and complacency stemming from past successes. According to Respondent 14, "*Tiwala kami ta ajay inubra mi mit di napalabas kit mayat eh*". (We are confident that what we did last time is good) (Respondent 14, personal communication, April 28, 2023). This is supported by Sanderson (2022), who explained that groupthink includes a tendency for groups to be overconfident in making decisions for at least three distinct reasons, like a tendency to overestimate, invulnerability and morality. They also face pressure to conform, driven by the fear of conflict and the desire for harmony. These similarities indicate a shared tendency to suppress diverse perspectives and dissenting opinions.

Moreover, Respondent 3 mentioned that when the chairman expresses something, they agree, suggesting a tendency to conform rather than voice their thoughts or opinions. She stated that, "*Saka nu ana ti ibaga ni chairman nukwa kit wen lattan sigē lattan*" (... and if the Chairman says something, I say yes and agree) (Respondent 3, personal communication, April 29, 2023). Groupthink in political situations, as noted by Kenton (2022), poses significant risks. With limited individual expertise, there is a heightened likelihood of conforming to the group consensus or influencing others. This fosters a false sense of unanimity, encouraging members to conceal their doubts and increasing the pressure to conform.

However, variations exist in the antecedents related to structural faults. San Bonifacio stands out with an authoritarian leadership style, characterized by centralized decision-making power, which suppresses independent thinking and diverse viewpoints. Respondent 1 shared, "*Kaso meron din yung minsan pag may sessions yung opinion na yung nasusunod*." But there are also times when we have sessions where his opinion is what we follow (Respondent 1, personal communication, April 29, 2023).

In addition, the researcher's observations during their monthly session reveal that the chairman's decisions are unquestioningly followed by the group. Moreover, the chairman does not seek the opinions of their officials but rather promptly shares his own decisions. This behavior exemplifies an authoritarian leadership style, where the leader exercises significant control and authority over the group without actively soliciting input or fostering collaborative decision-making processes. According to groupthink theory, authoritarian leadership style can lead to groupthink by limiting independent thinking, critical analysis, and diverse viewpoints. In this style, the leader's opinions and directives are unquestioningly followed, resulting in flawed decision-making and the suppression of individual autonomy within the group.

Additionally, Barangay San Miguel highlights distractions during decision-making, such as emergency meetings, leading to hasty decisions without considering consequences. One response suggests that distractions can occur during group decision-making processes, "*Siguro ajay nu maminsan kit adda panpanunatik nga sabali*." (Maybe when I'm thinking different things, I just agree with what they want to happen.) (Respondent 6, personal communication, April 28, 2023). In connection with that, Boles (2021) asserted that several factors, including workplace stressors such as distraction, noise, and workload, can influence the quality of decision-making. These findings were also supported by the idea of Baptist (2015), which says disruption lowers the chances of a sound choice being made.

On the other hand, bounded rationality was emphasized in San Miguel, where decisions are based on the belief that the majority's viewpoint is the best course of action, neglecting alternative perspectives and individual input. This reflects Alkousseify's (2015) study in which he claimed that bounded rationality could possibly lead to

groupthink. According to him, bounded rationality assumes that the decision-maker lacks the time, space, and ability to arrive at an ideal answer and that many people do not aim to optimize at all. Individuals seek to be reasonable after drastically simplifying their options.

Outcomes Of Group Cohesion and Groupthink Emergence

The transformation of group cohesion into groupthink in Barangay San Bonifacio leads to member dissatisfaction with the chairman's decisions, undermining unity and causing perceptions of ineffective leadership.

One decision that caused discord was the rejection of a proposed field trip for barangay officials. The chairman dismissed the idea, causing a sense of exclusion and undermining group cohesion. Additionally, the chairman's habit of canceling activities further frustrates members. Parraza (2018) provides backing to this concept, suggesting that groupthink involves a tendency towards seeking agreement without considering alternatives, disregarding individual objectives, neglecting risk assessment, displaying bias in decision-making, and lacking contingency plans.

Furthermore, the case of Barangay San Bonifacio served as an example that highlighted the negative outcomes resulting from the transformation of group cohesion into groupthink, leading to discontent among its members. In San Miguel and Raniag, project delays occur due to groupthink, hindering critical thinking, coordination, and decision-making. Respondent 10 said, "*Madelay jay project nga ubrain mi kuma...*" (The project that we were planning to work on was delayed...) (Respondent 10, personal communication, April 26, 2023). The insights from Adcock Solution (2022) align with these findings, stressing the significance of thorough decision-making discussions to prevent project delays.

In Barangay San Miguel, poor decision-making led to failure-induced shame and personal accountability. This is evident as the respondent mentioned being presented to the higher court, the Sangguniang Bayan, indicating that their decision was challenged or questioned. The respondent expressed embarrassment and shame for their actions, suggesting that they believe they should have handled the situation differently or made a better decision. This situation reflects the experiences of former US President John F. Kennedy during the Bay of Pigs tragedy in 1961, highlighting the dangers of groupthink. Kennedy's reliance on advisors who either agreed with him or hesitated to disagree resulted in a poorly executed operation and subsequent embarrassment (Discover DHL, 2023).

Similar to the data obtained from Barangay San Bonifacio, groupthink among barangay officials in San Miguel and Raniag also led to constituent dissatisfaction as well as limited resources, and miscommunication. Further, in Barangay San Miguel, groupthink resulted in a lack of risk oversight during project planning, posing potential harm to stakeholders.

Respondent 9 mentioned project delays attributed to the influence of a powerful individual, indicating a potential imbalance of power in decision-making. Additionally, a situation where a cockpit was located close to a school and a road without considering the negative outcome, resulting in inappropriate language being heard by children, was highlighted. This relates to Cherry's (2022) idea that, groupthink can lead people to disregard crucial information, resulting in poor decision-making posing the potential for risk oversight.

In addition, insufficient financial resources in Barangay Raniag force individuals to cover expenses with personal funds, leading to wasted time and effort. The result coincides with Reaves' (2018) idea, in which he stated that managers face challenges when dealing with projects that exceed the budget, lack adequate resources, or have unrealistic expectations. In such situations, groupthink tends to emerge as the project spirals out of control.

Lastly, role overload occurred in Barangay Raniag, where individuals shoulder excessive work and responsibilities due to past shortcomings. Respondent 11 answered, "*Masasabi ko na kapinsa-pinsala kapag madodoble yung trabaho dahil sa mga kakulangan naming noong nakaraan.*" (I can say that it is disastrous when we have to double our efforts because of our shortcomings in the past.) (Respondent 11, personal communication, April 30, 2023). This idea aligns with the perspective presented by Lindley et al. (2018), who noted that an organization trapped in groupthink fails to acknowledge the excessive workload it imposes on itself. Due to a fear of disagreement, they readily accept any tasks and decisions put forth by the group, even if they exceed their anticipated workload. This situation can lead to stress and anxiety among individuals within the organization.

Strategies To Prevent Groupthink and Enhance Decision-Making

In Barangay San Bonifacio, promoting communication and participation to prevent groupthink involves valuing diverse opinions and listening to everyone's suggestions. According to Openstax (2022), it is stated there

that having more individual suggestions during decision-making is also essential, as each individual provides unique information or knowledge to the group as well as diverse viewpoints on the situation.

Planning ahead, gathering relevant information, and discussing problems among Kagawads before approaching the chairman are essential for effective decision-making. Emphasizing fairness ensures that all viewpoints are considered and biased decision-making is avoided. They understood that insufficient preparation could contribute to groupthink, as decisions might rely solely on initial opinions and limit critical thinking. To counteract this, San Bonifacio stressed the need for thorough planning before making any decisions. Kishore's (2020) study emphasizes the importance of comprehensive planning and thorough preparation in decision-making. According to the study, effective decision-making involves proactively planning ahead and preparing in a manner that enables the consideration of multiple options.

Meanwhile, in Barangay San Miguel, a thorough decision-making process is emphasized to prevent groupthink. Thorough decision-making involves careful study, considering alternatives, having backup plans, and seeking advice from experts. It was also mentioned in San Miguel that collaboration with external sources brings fresh perspectives and breaks away from groupthink.

By actively seeking advice from external sources, Barangay San Bonifacio demonstrated their willingness to tap into a broader knowledge base beyond their immediate community. Consulting experts from the Department of Health or the Municipality allowed them to benefit from specialized insights and up-to-date information related to public health, governance, or other relevant areas. The data gathered is similar to what Lau (2023) stated in his study, in which he stated that it is essential to seek advice from an outside expert to avoid groupthink because it can help clarify ideas and pinpoint the strengths and flaws of ideas.

Lastly, strategies include education and development of barangay officials through seminars enhance knowledge and skills. By providing opportunities for continuous learning and development, the barangay ensures its officials are well-equipped with the skills necessary for informed decision-making. This commitment to education further strengthened their ability to avoid groupthink and make more effective decisions. This is reaffirmed in the research carried out by Davidson (2019), where it is argued that in order to steer clear of the pitfalls of groupthink, team members should possess a solid educational background and are advised to actively participate in seminars or training sessions as a means to promote personal growth and acquire new knowledge that can be effectively utilized in the group's decision-making processes.

Additionally, in Barangay Raniag, active participation, open communication, and incorporating diverse opinions are encouraged. These strategies collectively emphasize the significance of communication, participation, thorough preparation, fairness, collaboration with external sources, education, and development in preventing groupthink and enhancing decision-making in the barangay context.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The study found strong group cohesion in the selected barangays, but officials faced challenges in decision-making including doubts, self-censorship, hierarchical structures, and gender stereotyping. The presence of groupthink antecedents such as the illusion of unanimity and blind obedience to authority were confirmed. Respondents identified strategies like open communication, diverse viewpoints, thorough planning, fairness, collaboration with external sources, and continuous education as effective in avoiding groupthink and improving decision-making quality.

Notably, San Bonifacio stood out for its comprehensive approach, promoting inclusive decision-making and critical thinking while avoiding groupthink. These findings highlight the complexity of decision-making in barangays and the importance of overcoming challenges and implementing effective strategies. In comparison, San Miguel and Raniag shared some strategies to prevent groupthink, but their approach was not as comprehensive as San Bonifacio's. San Bonifacio emphasized open communication, thorough planning, collaboration with external sources, and continuous learning, which were not explicitly mentioned by San Miguel and Raniag.

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